

BEFORE SCHOOL EDUCATION IN THE ORGANIZATION THE SCHOOL 'S COOPERATION WITH PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

M.Z. Faizullayeva

Directors and specialists of pre-school educational organizations
senior teacher of the institute of retraining and improvement of their
qualifications . Tashkent , Uzbekistan
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Har one of us of our child healthy , of course mature a person being adult enough we want However , to this reach for only one of desire the only one enough does not Our children you our our support , our attitude and of course each bilaterally our care with so to the degree achieves _

Today, in our country, gradual and large-scale reforms are being carried out in the education of the young generation as perfect human beings. In this way, the reforms implemented in the preschool education system are of particular importance.

In the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Training" dated December 16, 2019 No. 595, "Preschool **education and training is** to provide education and training to children, to develop them intellectually, morally, ethically, aesthetically and It was defined as a type of continuous education aimed at physical development and preparation of children for general secondary education.

In the process of reform, the tasks, contents, forms and methods of education and upbringing of children, as well as the priority directions of the development of pedagogic science are covered.

Today 's schoolchildren need not only clear knowledge, but also thinking skills, understanding adults and classmates, and cooperation with them. Therefore, when a child enters school, it is more important not to have knowledge, but his readiness to acquire new knowledge, the ability to adapt to the environment, to independently analyze events and act.

It is important not only to teach a child something, but also to gain confidence in one's own strength, to protect one's ideas, to form the ability to make decisions independently.

The need to establish cooperative relations between pre-school education organizations and the school remains relevant at the moment. Research and experience show that strong cooperation between educators and primary school teachers contributes positively to children's development and education. Person-centered education is based on the belief that this partnership is necessary to enhance and expand the education provided in preschool organizations, as well as to develop interest and learning that occurs at home and in the community. Partnership means that both parties have rights and obligations, recognize each other as competent, and value each other as partners. Partnerships require that elementary teachers who work with caregivers recognize and appreciate the many important ways in which they contribute to children's learning and development. Primary school

teachers who work with preschool children make instructional recommendations based on what educators are teaching at Preschool .

In the preschool education organization, they provide advice and guidance in preparing children for school education, including teaching literacy, forming mathematical ideas, and teaching visual activities.

In the process of cooperation, primary school teachers observed and analyzed the educational activities of educators during the "Open Doors" day, which was organized as part of educational activities aimed at the development of speech and literacy for the students of the preparatory group for school. can be taught in many ways. The method of teaching literacy in the pre-school education system has its own characteristics, which begins with the formation of elementary reading and writing skills.

Reading and writing is a type of speech activity. Ability to perform reading and writing actions appropriately during literacy training is called reading and writing skills. Reading and writing skills are gradually improved and become proficient is converted. Both reading skills and writing skills are formed in an integral connection with other types of speech activity, that is, oral storytelling, listening to other people's speech, inner speech.

Primary school teachers and educators work together to ensure that the development of preschool children's reading and writing skills is carried out organically and continuously.

B primary teachers are required to take into account the unique features of the Uzbek language system of sounds and letters in the methodology of teaching literacy, and the educator plans activities taking into account the phonetic features of the Uzbek language during the literacy training process. necessity, for this he recommends that it is important to take into account the features of the graphic system of the Uzbek language, and to properly organize literacy, to teach preschool children to read on a step-by-step basis, step-by-step It is important to divide words into syllables and determine syllable boundaries in order to teach them to read aloud. helps him to distinguish words, to make words from syllables with the help of syllabic cards.

In the formation of elementary mathematical concepts in children, the educator uses various teaching methods - practical, instructive, oral, game methods. When choosing a method, primary school teachers give recommendations to educators , taking into account the age and individual characteristics of children , the availability of necessary didactic tools, etc.

mathematics classes of elementary school teachers to educators , to practice counting objects according to the specified number, from 0 to 9 introducing the numbers, training children to find the previous and next number for each of the numbers from 1-10; Strengthen understanding of the ratio between numbers 1-10; to say the name of a number in correct and reverse order starting from the desired number, understand the expressions "before and after", "before and after", count in order up to 10, distinguish between quantity and order of counting, "how many?", "which?" , "how much is it?" to be able to answer the questions correctly, to practice determining the number of the same and different objects up to 10 located in different positions (in a circle, in a square, in a row), to teach counting from 1 to 20 they give recommendations on the use of methods, the game "Tangram" (geometric constructor), various exhibitions.

In conclusion, more effective organization of cooperation with schools and contribution to their development is defined as one of the priority tasks of pedagogues . Such cooperation between MTT and schools will undoubtedly bear fruit in the near future.

References:

1. F.R. Valieva To Develop Professional Training of Professionals Education Specialists by Ensuring // International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD) Special Issue on International Research Development and Scientific Excellence in Academic Life Available Online: www.ijtsrd.com e-ISSN: 2456 – 6470 2021 /
2. F.R. Valieva, Abdunazarova Nargiza Fatkhullaevna, Zakirov Alisher Akbarovich SCOPUS. The importance of ensuring the mental, physical, spiritual, spiritual development of educators of pre-school educational organizations . PhD. Valieva Feruza Rashidovna //Bosma //Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TAJQI) Volume 12, Issue 8. July. 2021:6919.
3. Resolution No. 802 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 22, 2020 "On approval of the state standard of preschool education and upbringing".
4. "Ilk Kadam" state curriculum for preschool educational organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2nd edition), 2022 .
5. Kadirova F.R. and others. "Preschool pedagogy" (textbook). Tashkent, "Taffakkur" 2019.
6. G. Kh. Kadyrova Pedagogicheskie usloviya tvorcheskogo samorazvitiya seniorsheklassnika v kreativnom obrazovanii // Innovatsionnoe razvitie nauk obrazovanie. Collection of international distance conference. - Kazakhstan, 2020. - P.197-199.